

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Faziljanova Nilufar Khikmatjanovna

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Abstract: This article discusses the implementation of distance learning technologies in the practice of primary education to enhance learning efficiency. It explores the advantages and disadvantages of distance learning and addresses the pedagogical foundations for integrating these technologies. Relevant proposals and conclusions are provided.

Keywords: distance learning, pedagogy, primary education, teaching, upbringing, distance, methodology, form, features, tools, approach, knowledge, skills.

In today's world, the development of modern technologies has brought a series of changes and innovations to the education system. One of the convenient methods created for students to acquire education is distance learning. In Uzbekistan, as in other developed countries, particular attention is paid to the development of computer and information technologies. The Presidential Decree of May 30, 2002, "On further development of computerization and implementation of information and communication technologies," along with relevant decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers and the Ministry of Public Education's directives, serves as a basis for forming a national system of informatization, introducing modern information technologies in all sectors, and expanding access to global information resources.

Distance learning is a modern form of organizing the educational process where the teacher and student are not in the same location. This form of education is primarily implemented using the Internet, computer technologies, and digital platforms. Distance learning not only simplifies the educational process but also bridges geographical distances, opening new opportunities for teachers and students.

These tools of distance learning are highly effective even in complex situations. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the education system in our country implemented teaching processes through television. Observations indicate that primary school students participated in such educational processes with interest and enthusiasm. Their level of comprehension was satisfactory as well. Thus, online forms of distance learning deliver the expected results. Integrating distance learning technologies into the primary education process is

of great importance in modern educational practices. This process has several advantages.

Distance learning technologies provide educational opportunities for children in rural and remote areas. This ensures equal access to education. With the help of online platforms and programs, students can interact with educational materials. This increases their engagement and helps reinforce knowledge. Distance learning allows students to manage their time effectively. They can conduct lessons at a time and place convenient for them. Implementing distance learning technologies in primary education is essential to improving the quality of education and creating broader opportunities for students. By applying innovations in the education system, we can equip future generations with modern knowledge.

The most commonly used types of lessons in distance learning are:

1. Lessons introducing new knowledge.
2. Lessons for reinforcing previously taught material.
3. Lessons for checking and assessing students' knowledge, skills, and competencies.

4. Mixed lesson processes (combining several of the aforementioned types). Each type of lesson has a specific structure and features that help the teacher effectively explain, reinforce, and control the comprehension of the educational material. Pedagogical experiments have shown that in a distance learning environment, designing lesson processes using digital technologies develops students' abilities to perceive, analyze, and retain complex educational information through various visual aids, videos, graphics, and schematics. Distance learning is one of the significant forms of education in the modern era. Its advantages and opportunities contribute to further developing the education system. In Uzbekistan, improving technological infrastructure, training teachers in digital literacy, and ensuring equal opportunities for all students are critical for advancing distance learning.

References:

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 dated October 5, 2020, "On approving the Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 strategy and measures for its effective implementation" (Legislation Bulletin of the Republic of Uzbekistan, October 12, 2020, Issue 40, Article 443).
2. Jakbarov O., Madraximova M., Jakbarova D. Algorithm for developing a software product for learning the PREZI program // Materials of the republican scientific-practical conference on "Modern information and communication

- technologies in education: problems and solutions." — Namangan, NamSU, 2018. — P. 33-34.
3. M.I. Bazarboyev, I. Mullajonov, Biophysics. Tashkent, 2018. <https://elibrary.namdu.uz>
 4. Khaitov, A., & Yusupova, I. (2022). Methods for developing logical thinking competencies in primary school students based on an integrative approach. *Science and Innovation*, 1(B7), 1262-1267.
 5. Abrorxonova, K. A., & Feruza, N. (2023). Development of reading culture in primary classes. *Education, Science, and Innovative Ideas Worldwide*, 31(2), 160-163.
 6. Abrorxonova, K., & Murodova, M. (2022). Formation of linguistic competencies based on the analysis of word combinations. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 2082-2088.
 7. Anvar, H. Integrated Approach to Improving Pedagogical Abilities of Future Primary Education Teachers. *JournalNX*, 197-201.
 8. Abrorxonova, K. A. Q., & Bo'Riyeva, S. I. Q. (2023). Psychological possibilities of forming media culture in primary school students. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, Educational, Natural, and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 778-782.
 9. Abrorxonova, K., Rahmatova, F., & Dehqonboyev, M. (2022). Technology for forming the virtue of tolerance in primary class students. *Science and Innovation*, 1(7), 362-367.
 10. Khakimov, F. (2024). The role of digital technologies in the management of general secondary education institutions. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 4(02), 164-168.
 11. Khakimov, F. (2024). Methods for developing creative thinking skills in primary class students. *Confrencea*, 5, 89-92.
 12. Abrorxonova, K., & Pirnazarova, K. (2022). Development of research skills in primary school students. *Science and Innovation*, 1(B8), 2089-2096.

